

RELATIVE ABUNDANCE OF VERTEBRATE FOSSIL TAXA IN THE UPPER CRETACEOUS EXPOSURES OF MONMOUTH COUNTY BROOKS & A TEST OF SPECIES RICHNESS EXTRAPOLATORS

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ABSTRACT- A series of expeditions to Ramanessin Brook and Big Brook in Monmouth County, New Jersey, were conducted in 2021 and 2022 to collect fossils deposited in the streambed from the highly productive exposures of Upper Cretaceous sediment. Over 2500 individual specimens, representing at least 27 distinct vertebrate taxa, were collected, identified, and catalogued. The relative abundance of different vertebrate taxa from this collection is reported. Additionally, this large, multi-sample dataset was used to test the applicability of various extrapolators of true species richness within the fossil record. These extrapolators are designed to estimate the total number of species present in any given community, accounting for those an observer is likely to have missed and could therefore be extremely useful for the study of biodiversity in the distant past. All extrapolators applied to this dataset produced estimates of vertebrate species richness lower than the actual number of taxa known to have been present in this paleocommunity, suggesting that they should be used with caution when researching biodiversity in the fossil record.

INTRODUCTION

The fossil record has long been recognized as the best source of data for long term trends in biodiversity in the Earth's past (Bush & Bambach, 2004; Phillips, 1860; Raup, 1976). Highly fossiliferous sites provide important glimpses into extinct communities and allow for comparison of biodiversity across broad spatial and temporal scales (Fritz et al., 2013; Nogués-Bravo et al., 2018; Yasuhara et al., 2017). Many of the brooks of Monmouth County, New Jersey, pass through highly fossiliferous sediment from the Upper Cretaceous System, and as such expose a number of significant fossil sites (Callahan et al., 2014).

These sites, including the popular localities along Big Brook and Ramanessin Brook, preserve fossils of marine and terrestrial organisms dating

from the Campanian and/or Maastrichtian Stages of the Cretaceous (Becker et al., 1996; B. Bennington, 2003; Callahan et al., 2014). The most commonly found and collected vertebrate fossils are the teeth of sharks, though remains of other vertebrate organisms such as bony fish, mosasaurs, occasional dinosaurs, and numerous invertebrate fossils are also found (Callahan et al., 2014). These fossils are well-known to professional paleontologists and amateur collectors alike, with Big Brook especially being a popular recreational site (Beard, 2013).

The majority of vertebrate fossils found in the brooks derive from the base of the Navesink Formation and the underlying Wenonah & Mount Laurel Formations. Further south, the Mount Laurel Formation is known to lie between the Wenonah and the Navesink, but it may have

been eroded away along sections of the Monmouth County brooks (B. Bennington, 2003; Callahan et al., 2014). Many of the vertebrate fossils found at these sites derive from highly concentrated fossiliferous layers or lag deposits (Callahan et al., 2014; Gallagher, 2014). One especially productive layer has usually been interpreted as a transgressive lag deposit that lies at the very base of the Navesink, but it has alternatively been suggested that this fossiliferous layer may have formed through marine and fluvial action during regressive conditions and should be interpreted as an uppermost portion of the Mount Laurel Formation (Callahan et al., 2014; Gallagher, 2014; Martino & Curran, 1990). This condensed layer of fossiliferous material overlies a disconformity representing a prolonged period of erosion or non-deposition lasting about 2 million years (Callahan et al., 2014; Garb et al., 2007).

The upper layers of the Navesink Formation preserve several other distinct facies which demonstrate a general transition from an inner shelf to an outer shelf environment as sea levels rose (B. Bennington, 2003). These higher facies are generally lacking in vertebrate fossils, though remains of invertebrates, especially the oysters, *Exogyra costata*, *Pycnodonte convexa*, and *Agerostrea mesenterica* are abundant in certain layers, whereas groundwater leaching has rendered such invertebrate fossils virtually absent from the lower layers which are richer in vertebrate material (B. Bennington, 2003; J. B. Bennington, 1996; Gallagher, 2014). These higher layers of the Navesink are widely exposed at Big Brook Preserve while only the more basal portions of the formation are exposed by accessible sections of Ramanessin Brook (B. Bennington, 2003; Callahan et al., 2014).

Although occurrences of numerous Cretaceous vertebrate taxa at the Monmouth County Brooks are well-documented in the literature, quantitative records of typical species-level abundance are lacking (Callahan et al., 2014; Gallagher, 2014; Lauginiger, 1986). Previous research has demonstrated that, at least among some paleocommunities, relative abundance of fossil species is largely representative of actual relative abundance of the living organisms, accounting for biases in preservation and sampling (Kidwell, 2001). However, when working with fossil teeth, especially those of sharks, numerous variables including taxonomic identity, feeding habits, and age affect rates of tooth loss, and therefore inherent biases exist in fossilization rates (Luer et al., 1990; Reif, 1976; Strasburg, 1963; Visaggi & Godfrey, 2010). Nevertheless, while the abundance of fossilized teeth and other isolated remains may not represent a reliable measure of the actual number of individuals, it still provides valuable paleoecological data in that it approximates the proportion of fossil remains left by various taxa (Visaggi & Godfrey, 2010).

While relative fossil abundance may not be indicative of true paleoecological dynamics, other metrics of biodiversity can still be observed in the fossil record. Species richness, or the total number of species present in a community, is perhaps the most intuitive way to measure biodiversity (R. Colwell, 2009). Species richness is an especially important metric, as it can be measured and compared at a variety of spatial and temporal scales, and thus provides insight into how biodiversity has changed throughout the Earth's history in response to changes in global and local climate (Alroy, 2010). However, as species vary widely in commonality, any single observer is likely to miss a number of rare species in any community, extant or extinct

(Sanders, 1968). To overcome this unevenness, numerous extrapolators have been developed which aim to derive estimates of true species richness from incomplete samples, accounting for the taxa the observer is likely to have missed (Burnham & Overton, 1978; Chao, 1984, 1987; Chao et al., 2000; R. K. Colwell et al., 2004; Rennolls & Laumonier, 2006; Smith & van Belle, 1984).

These extrapolators rely on resampling, or the generation of new, smaller samples within an observed sample and account for variables such as total sample size, number of observation periods, and species evenness to derive approximations of true species richness by estimating the number of species the observer likely missed in their entire sample. Therefore, they could represent highly useful tools for measuring and comparing biodiversity in the distant past using the fragmentary fossil record. However, while species richness extrapolators have been widely used to measure biodiversity in living communities, their application to the fossil record has so far been limited (Close et al., 2018). Researchers have recently tested the applicability of several of these extrapolators in the fossil record using hypothetical digital datasets, but they have not been widely used with actual fossil collections (Close et al., 2018).

As they yield countless fossils from a variety of taxa, the brooks of Monmouth County represent ideal localities for the study of biodiversity in the fossil record. Furthermore, as the brooks have been extensively studied for decades, they are represented by a dense literature including records of species occurrence. Therefore, these sites also represent an ideal system in which to test the performance of various species richness extrapolators in the fossil record.

This study draws from a collection of over 2500 fossils collected in 2021 and 2022 from the Upper Cretaceous formations exposed by Ramanessin and Big Brooks. A comprehensive report on the relative abundance of different vertebrate taxa is provided. Additionally, this collection is used as a sample dataset for a number of species richness extrapolators to better assess their applicability to the study of biodiversity in the fossil record.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Between May 2021 and August 2022, vertebrate fossils were collected along Ramanessin Brook, just north of Monmouth County Route 520, and along Big Brook at Big Brook Preserve. The exposed sections at these sites differ significantly, with the higher portions of the Navesink Formation only exposed at Big Brook, though the fossiliferous transgressive/regressive deposit is exposed along both sections of stream (B. Bennington, 2003; Callahan et al., 2014). As a result, while the vertebrate assemblages of the two sites are largely the same, the invertebrate faunas of the two sites are not comparable, with a far more diverse assemblage being preserved at Big Brook. To maximize consistency in sampling, and because the invertebrate fauna of Big Brook has already been well quantified, only vertebrate fossils collected from each site were considered in biodiversity analyses (B. Bennington, 2003; J. B. Bennington, 2003). Additionally, as vertebrate fossils were observed to be more numerous along Ramanessin Brook, most sampling occurred at the Ramanessin site.

Fossils were collected using three general methods:

1. Most fossils were collected by-hand while walking along the banks of the Brooks. Visible fossils lying amidst gravel along the streambanks, underwater on the

streambed, or exposed in-situ within the sediment of the surrounding formation were collected by hand.

2. Gravel lying either on the streambanks or underwater in the streambed was collected with a small spade and placed into a sifting screen. A ¼" screen was primarily used though a ½" screen was less frequently used as well. After thoroughly shaking it just under the surface of the water in order to remove all sand and small pebbles, the screen, now filled with fossiliferous gravel was rushed under water in order to remove as much modern organic debris as possible. The gravel inside the screen was then meticulously picked for fossils.
3. Fine-grained sediment was collected from the brooks and transported in plastic bags to off-site facilities. Sediment was then washed in a controlled setting and sifted using a very fine 1 mm screen so that microfossils could be collected. To preserve the integrity of the sites, sediment collection was minimal.

In total, 41 samples representing 2602 individual specimens were collected, 2376 along Ramanessin Brook and 226 from Big Brook Preserve. All fossils were stored in plastic bags representing the date and sample from which they were collected. Fossils were assigned to taxa based on a variety of morphological characters outlined in descriptions provided by previous research (Callahan et al., 2014; Cappetta, 1987; Welton & Farish, 1993). In total, out of the 2602 total specimens collected, 1504 could be confidently assigned to at least 27 distinct vertebrate taxa. All fossils were numbered and catalogued in a spreadsheet which noted their assigned field number, taxonomic identification, location, date, and any specific notes about their morphology.

Following collection and identification of all vertebrate specimens, this database was used to test the applicability of 12 species richness extrapolators in the fossil record. All analyses were processed using R statistical software, specifically with the package 'wiqid' designed by Meredith et al. and the 'TRiPS' code designed by Starrfelt and Liow (Meredith et al., 2022; R Core Team, 2020; Starrfelt & Liow, 2015). The 'wiqid' package includes a number of commonly used species richness extrapolators, 11 of which were compared in this study (Chao, 1984, 1987; Chao et al., 2000; Gotelli & Colwell, 2011; R. K. Colwell et al., 2004; Rennolls & Laumonier, 2006; Smith & van Belle, 1984;). These extrapolators vary in their conceptualization and derivation, but all rely on resampling within the observed sample to estimate the number of species missed by the observer and extrapolate the true species richness in the community.

Additionally, Starrfelt and Liow's 'TRiPS' (True Richness estimated using a Poisson Sampling model) estimator for species richness was tested using the script provided in their original manuscript (Starrfelt & Liow, 2015). This extrapolator was specifically designed to account for biases within the fossil record when estimating species richness in the distant past and is therefore of special interest for this study (Starrfelt & Liow, 2015).

After estimates of species richness in had been derived by applying each extrapolator to this dataset using R, the performance of each extrapolator could be assessed by comparing to the number of fossil vertebrate species actually known from the brooks. Publicly-available records of species incidence drawing on hundreds of years of collection efforts indicate that at least 49 distinct vertebrate taxa were present in this Late Cretaceous marine

ecosystem (Callahan et al., 2014; Case, 1995; Case et al., 2001; Case & Cappetta, 2004; Cope, 1871; Fowler & Kümmel, 1911; Leidy, 1873; Lauginiger, 1986; Russell & Gauthier, 2020). Therefore, for any of these extrapolators to be considered reliable tools for measuring richness in the fossil record, they should estimate that at least 49 taxa were present in the community represented by this dataset.

However, as in-situ sampling was limited, micro-vertebrate fossils (<5 mm) were likely underrepresented in this collection. To account for this, the dataset was filtered so that only species represented by macrofossils were included in the extrapolations. The species richness extrapolators were then applied to this subset of the entire dataset to yield estimates of the true richness of vertebrates with fossils larger than 5 mm. As with the entire dataset, these estimates could then be compared to records of species incidence at the Brooks to determine their validity. In this case, at least 37 distinct vertebrate taxa have been identified from the assemblage of macrofossils collected from the Brooks (Callahan et al., 2014; Case, 1995; Case et al., 2001; Case & Cappetta, 2004; Cope, 1871; Fowler & Kümmel, 1911; Leidy, 1873; Lauginiger, 1986; Russell & Gauthier, 2020). Therefore, to be considered valid, each extrapolator should yield an estimate of at least 37 species present in the community represented by this subset of the data.

RESULTS

Of the 2602 total specimens collected, 2368 were identified as fossils of extinct vertebrates. A significant portion (863) of these fossils consisted of isolated or badly worn elements (badly worn teeth, bone fragments, isolated vertebrae, etc.) which could not be assigned to any particular species or genus, leaving 1505

specimens which could confidently be assigned to a specific taxon. Additionally, due to the undiagnostic nature of many isolated elements and current gaps in the taxonomy of several groups represented in the Brooks, a number of specimens could only be assigned to the genus or family level (e.g., “*Meristodonoides* sp.” or “crocodyliformes”). In these instances, all specimens were assumed to represent the same taxon. Thus, the actual number of taxa represented by this dataset is likely higher than what is presented.

Across both sites, shark teeth dominate the vertebrate assemblage. Worn lamniform teeth which could not be confidently assigned to a single species were common. Of the remains which could be confidently assigned to an individual species or distinct taxonomic grouping, sharks and other chondrichthyans represent over 75% of all specimens. Among the sharks, the goblin shark, *Scapanorhynchus texanus* was by far the most abundant, though the crow sharks, *Squalicorax lindstromi* and *Squalicorax pristodontis*, as well as two species of mackerel sharks, *Archaeolamna kopingensis* and *Cretalamna appendiculata*, were also very common. Several species of sand tiger sharks, especially *Carcharias samhammeri*, were well-represented and, based on the morphology and generally small size of their teeth, a large portion of the unidentifiable shark teeth may have belonged to these sand tiger sharks. Other rarer species of sharks included the hybodont, *Meristodonoides* sp., the thresher shark, *Paranomotodon angustidens*, and several species represented only by microfossils such as the angel shark, *Squatina hassei*. Various species of non-shark chondrichthyans including rays, skates, and chimera were also represented, with the “sawskate”, *Ischyrrhiza mira* being especially common (Greenfield, 2021).

Non-chondrichthyan vertebrate remains were also prevalent. Among the bony fish, the teeth and palatine bones of *Enchodus*, particularly *E. petrosus*, dominated the assemblage, though teeth of another species, *E. gladiolus*, were also relatively common. Other species of fish including *Anomoedus phaseolus*, *Hadrodus priscus*, *Pachyrhizodus* sp., and *Xiphactinus* sp. were also represented.

Isolated fragments of indeterminate reptile bone were relatively common. Among identifiable

reptile remains, mosasaur teeth were most prevalent, though they still made up less than one percent of the total vertebrate assemblage. Most mosasaur teeth were attributed to *Mosasaurus conodon*, though one was assigned to the rare species, *Liodon sectorius*. Other reptile remains consisted of isolated crocodylian teeth and scutes as well as turtle shell fragments. Graphical breakdowns of total and relative vertebrate species abundance are provided in figures 1 and 2 respectively, with Table 1 providing a more complete summary of all vertebrate remains.

Figure 1: Total abundance of different species and distinct taxa collected along Ramanessin and Big Brooks in this study. Numbers above columns indicate total number of specimens found of each species or taxa.

Figure 2: Relative abundance of different species and distinct taxa collected along Ramanessin and Big Brooks in this study. Numbers above columns indicate the percentage of the total identified fossil vertebrate assemblage represented by each species or taxa.

Taxa	Abundance	Description of Material
Chondrichthyes		
Chondrichthyes indet.	757	Teeth, vertebrae, coprolites
Sharks		
<i>Scapanorhynchus texanus</i>	550	Teeth
<i>Squalicorax lindstromi</i>	236	Teeth
<i>Archaeolamna kopingensis</i>	77	Teeth
<i>Cretalamna appendiculata</i>	75	Teeth
<i>Carcharias samhammeri</i>	60	Teeth
<i>Squalicorax pristodontis</i>	46	Teeth
<i>Eostriatolamia holmdelensis</i>	19	Teeth
<i>Paranomotodon angustidens</i>	7	Teeth
<i>Meristodonoides sp.</i>	6	Teeth, cephalic clasper
<i>Squatina hassei</i>	3	Teeth
<i>Protalamna borodini</i>	2	Teeth
<i>Odontaspis aculaeatus</i>	1	Tooth
Skates & Rays		
<i>Ischyrrhiza mira</i>	59	Rostral spines, oral teeth
<i>Brachyrhizodus wichitaensis</i>	9	Teeth
<i>Rhombodus laevis</i>	2	Tooth, dermal denticle
<i>Ptychotrygon sp.</i>	1	Tooth
Chimaera		
<i>Ischyodus bifurcatus</i>	14	Jaw fragments
Osteichthyes		
Osteichthyes indet.	106	Vertebrae, bone fragments, teeth
Bony Fish		
<i>Enchodus petrosus</i>	236	Teeth, jaw fragments
<i>Enchodus gladiolus</i>	43	Teeth
<i>Anomoeodus phaseolus</i>	20	Teeth
<i>Hadrodus priscus</i>	12	Pharyngeal teeth
<i>Pachyrhizodus sp.</i>	3	Teeth
<i>Xiphactinus sp.</i>	3	Teeth
Reptiles		
<i>Mosasaurus conodon</i>	12	Teeth
Crocodyliformes indet.	6	Teeth, scutes
Testudines indet.	2	Carapace Fragments
<i>Liodon sectorius</i>	1	Tooth

Table 1: Abundance and brief description of various types of vertebrate fossils found along Ramanessin and Big Brooks in this study.

At least 27 vertebrate taxa were represented in this sample. Following identification of all specimens, this dataset was analyzed using R to test 12 different species richness extrapolators. Estimates of true vertebrate species richness in this paleocommunity derived from the application of these extrapolators to this dataset are provided in Table 2. Of the 12 extrapolators tested, none yielded an estimate of richness which matched or exceeded the actual number of vertebrate taxa known from the brooks (49).

Additionally, in order to account for potential sampling biases, estimates of vertebrate species richness for this paleocommunity were also calculated based only on the 23 taxa represented by macrofossils in this sample, as sampling for microfossils (<5 mm) was less consistent. Table 3 therefore provides estimates of true richness of vertebrate species which could be represented by macrofossils. Even after filtering the dataset, all estimates of richness fell below the actual number of macro-vertebrate fossil taxa reliably recorded at the Brooks (37).

Extrapolator	Estimate	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	S.D.
Chao's Abundance-Based Coverage Estimator	30.079			
Chao's Incidence-Based Coverage Estimator	30.429			
"Chao 1"	31.000	27.557	55.720	5.292
"Chao 2"	39.500	28.665	120.834	17.139
First Order Incidence-Based Jackknife	31.878			
Second Order Incidence-Based Jackknife	35.707			
First Order Abundance-Based Jackknife	31.000			
Second Order Abundance-Based Jackknife	33.000			
Bootstrap Estimator	29.083			
Asymptotic (Michaelis-Menten) Estimator	27.094			
"Shadow-Species" Abundance-Based Estimator	29.000			
"TRiPS"	27.000	27.000	27.000	

Table 2: Estimations of true species richness derived from entire collection of vertebrate fossils. Estimates indicate the total number of vertebrate species present in the Monmouth County Late Cretaceous marine paleocommunity. When applicable, lower bound, upper bound, and standard deviation of estimates are provided. Note: at least 49 species of vertebrates are actually known from records of fossils found at the Brooks.

Extrapolator	Estimate	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	S.D.
Chao's Abundance-Based Coverage Estimator	26.050			
Chao's Incidence-Based Coverage Estimator	25.498			
"Chao 1"	28.500	24.495	64.917	7.194
"Chao 2"	28.500	24.495	64.917	7.194
First Order Incidence-Based Jackknife	26.927			
Second Order Incidence-Based Jackknife	28.853			
First Order Abundance-Based Jackknife	27.000			
Second Order Abundance-Based Jackknife	29.000			
Bootstrap Estimator	25.312			
Asymptotic (Michaelis-Menten) Estimator	24.226			
"Shadow-Species" Abundance-Based Estimator	26.000			
"TRiPS"	23.000	23.000	23.000	

Table 3: Estimations of true species richness derived from collection of vertebrate fossils incorporating only species represented by macrofossils. Estimates indicate the total number of macro-vertebrate species present in the Monmouth County Late Cretaceous marine paleocommunity. When applicable, lower bound, upper bound, and standard deviation of estimates are provided. Note: at least 37 species of vertebrates are actually known from records of macrofossils found at the Brooks.

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

At least 27 distinct species of vertebrate species were recorded in this fossil collection from the Brooks of Monmouth County. Within this relatively large collection, certain species were found to be extremely common, while others were only represented by a singular specimen. While the recorded abundances of various taxa may not be entirely representative of their actual relative abundances in the Cretaceous marine community, these results at least provide insight as to the relative rates at which different species are preserved and ultimately observed within the fossil record at these sites.

When applied to this dataset, all species richness extrapolators tested yielded estimates less than the actual number of taxa known from the Brooks. Failure to accurately estimate total richness is not surprising due to the highly uneven nature of the assemblage (i.e., some species are abundant while others are extremely rare), even considering the relatively extensive

coverage of this sample (Close et al., 2018; O'hara, 2005; Pielou, 1966). Even after taxa represented only by microfossils were removed from the sample to increase evenness, all estimations of true richness still fell significantly below the number (at least 37) of vertebrate species known from macrofossils (Callahan et al., 2014; Case, 1995; Case et al., 2001; Case & Cappetta, 2004; Cope, 1871; Fowler & Kümmel, 1911; Leidy, 1873; Lauginiger, 1986; Russell & Gauthier, 2020). Notably, TRiPS, a model specifically designed for estimating true richness in the fossil record, failed to account for any species not observed within the dataset, likely due to the large size of the sample and relatively complete coverage.

These data indicate that all these species richness extrapolators may fail to accurately estimate the total number of taxa present within fossil communities. Even this large, well-covered dataset from two highly productive sites yielded estimates well below the actual number of

vertebrate species known from records of incidence at the brooks. Therefore, when possible, it is suggested that studies of biodiversity in the distant past draw upon records of species occurrence and abundance from a variety of sources and datasets. Furthermore, while it is clear that these models underestimate true richness, it is uncertain if the margin of error would be consistent between different sites subject to differing taphonomic biases, and thus it is unclear if they could be used in comparative studies of biodiversity across time and space. Regardless, the data collected in this study provide valuable insight into the relative abundance of different fossil vertebrate taxa from the Late Cretaceous marine ecosystem preserved in present-day Monmouth County.

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